
118. The ‘plane of satellites’ problem

SINCE THE emergence of the Λ CDM parameterisation of the standard ‘big bang’ cosmological model in the late 1990s, various difficulties emerged in reconciling numerical simulations with observations at small (i.e. galaxy) scales. These include the ‘missing satellites’ problem, the ‘core-cusp’ problem, the ‘too-big-to-fail’ problem, and the ‘plane of satellites’ problem.

A recent review of the status of these and other ‘challenges for Λ CDM’, and the possible modifications to the standard formalism that some are considering to address them, is given by Perivolaropoulos & Skara (2022).

I will summarise these four particular challenges, then look in more detail at the ‘plane of satellites’ problem, and in particular how Gaia observations have recently been used, the authors suggest, to resolve it.

A WIDE RANGE of observations (including large-scale structures, the cosmic microwave background radiation and baryon acoustic oscillations, type Ia supernovae, and strong and weak lensing) suggest that only 5% of the current energy budget of the Universe consists of known forms of matter (mainly baryons), while the rest seems to be of unknown nature, comprising (it is believed) 27% dark matter and 68% dark energy.

The observations are generally interpreted as implying an equation of state for the dark energy to be close to that of a de Sitter space-time, $w \approx -1$, corresponding to a positive cosmological-constant, $\Lambda > 0$. In the so-called ‘lambda cold dark matter’ (Λ CDM) model, some form of ‘dark energy’ is responsible for the non-zero Λ , while the hypothesised ‘cold’ dark matter corresponds to particle masses > 100 keV, at least for the dominant component.

While particle physics models, in particular supersymmetry, provide candidates for the dark matter, no experimental evidence for it has been found to date.

LET ME first make a synopsis of the first three of these problems to provide some context. They essentially arose because the cold dark matter particles, which the simulations rely on, resulted in overly clumped and too numerous structures compared to those observed.

The ‘missing satellites’, or ‘dwarf galaxy’ problem, emerged from numerical simulations which demonstrated the hierarchical clustering of dark matter, in which smaller halos merge to form larger halos. In the earliest simulations, normal-sized galaxies were well reproduced, while the number of known dwarf galaxies was significantly lower than expected (e.g. Moore et al., 1999). I have touched on this problem, and its possible resolution, in essay #31 on dwarf spheroidal galaxies.

The ‘core-cusp’ problem emerged because simulations formed dark matter halos with ‘cuspy’ dark matter distributions, with the density increasing steeply at small radii, while the rotation curves of most dwarf galaxies indicate flat central density profiles or cores (e.g. de Blok, 2010; Errani et al., 2023).

The ‘too big to fail’ problem is a discrepancy between the most massive sub-haloes predicted, and the observed dynamics of the brightest dwarf spheroidal galaxies in the Local Group. The simulations predict that the most massive sub-haloes of the Local Group are too dense to host any of its bright satellites (e.g. Boylan-Kolchin et al., 2012; Lovell & Zavala, 2023).

THE ‘plane of satellites’ question is somewhat different: both major galaxies in the Local Group host planar distributions of orbiting satellite galaxies, constituting the ‘Vast Polar Structure’ of the Milky Way, and the ‘Great Plane of Andromeda’ (Kroupa et al., 2005; Conn et al., 2013; Ibata et al., 2014; Pawlowski et al., 2014; Pawlowski, 2018). And, within each of these systems, their orbits appear to be correlated (Pawlowski et al., 2012; Ibata et al., 2013; Sohn et al., 2020).

Their flattened structure and coherent motions are considered inconsistent with the Λ CDM model, as inferred from simulations, which instead indicate uncorrelated and nearly isotropic satellite systems (e.g. Libeskind et al., 2005; Zentner et al., 2005; Pawlowski, 2018).

In such cosmological simulations, structures with these sorts of spatial and kinematic coherences are (very) rare, with a probability of occurrence of order 10^{-3} (Pawlowski et al., 2014; Pawlowski, 2018).

I WILL NOW focus on the 11 ‘classical’ satellite galaxies of the Milky Way, organised in a thin plane that might be rotationally supported (Metz et al., 2008).

Pawlowski (2018) summarised the situation at the time by stating that similarly anisotropic phase-space distributions of sub-halos are exceedingly rare in cosmological simulations based on the Λ CDM paradigm and, in contrast to other small-scale problems, the satellite planes issue is not strongly affected by baryonic processes because the distribution of sub-halos on scales of hundreds of kpc is dominated by gravitational effects. He concluded that ‘... *this makes the satellite planes one of the most serious small-scale problems for Λ CDM*’.

Expressed alternatively, whereas energy dissipation can lead to the gas inside of galaxies settling into rotating thin disks, such a configuration is considered unlikely to form from the collisionless dark matter halo.

With no clear explanation within Λ CDM, the problem has been suggested as evidence for the modified gravity formulation MOND, in which the Milky Way’s satellite galaxies are dark-matter-free ‘tidal’ dwarf galaxies formed during a hypothetical past close encounter between the Milky Way and Andromeda (Famaey & McGaugh, 2012; Bilek et al., 2018; Banik et al., 2018).

WITH availability of the Gaia DR2 data, Pawlowski & Kroupa (2020) revisited the correlation of the orbital poles of these 11 satellite galaxies, confirming previous results on the degree of correlation and its significance. A majority of the satellites co-orbit along the Vast Polar Structure, the plane of the satellite galaxies being defined by their positions. The orbital planes of eight of the satellites align to $< 20^\circ$ with a common direction, with seven even orbiting in the same sense, and most also sharing similar specific angular momenta.

Combining the best-available proper motions thus appeared to *worsen* the tension with the Λ CDM expectations: less than 0.1% of simulated satellite systems in Illustris TNG (Vogelsberger et al., 2020) contain 7 orbital poles as closely aligned. Their results, they emphasised, compounded the ‘plane of satellites’ problem.

WITH EDR3, came greatly improved proper motions of many Local Group satellites, resulting in systemic motions for some 70 galaxies out to ~ 1.4 Mpc (McConnachie & Venn, 2020; Battaglia et al., 2022). These supplemented the positional and radial velocities from the earlier catalogue of McConnachie (2012).

An important (and somewhat unexpected) advance, based on these Gaia EDR3 data, was subsequently reported by Sawala et al. (2022). Based on the improved EDR3 proper motions, they examined the time evolution of the Milky Way satellite system, by numerically integration of the satellite orbits. These were considered as massless test particles in a static potential, consisting of a disk, stellar nucleus and bulge, and a dark matter halo.

Their simulations were based on initial conditions created for the Sibelius project (McAlpine et al., 2022), designed to reproduce Local Group analogues within the observed large-scale structure. They generated 60 000 simulations, resulting in several thousand loosely defined Local Group analogues. From these, they selected 101 for more detailed simulations, performed at a mass resolution of $1.0 \times 10^6 M_\odot$. At this resolution, a Milky Way analogue halo contains some 10^6 particles. An average of ~ 200 sub-halos down to $2 \times 10^7 M_\odot$ could then be identified within 300 kpc from the centre.

Their figure 2 (above) shows the most likely positions and estimated orbits of the 11 brightest satellites projected along the principal axes of inertia. In the bottom two panels, the grey horizontal line shows the ‘plane of satellites’ projected edge-on. Several satellites are presently crossing the plane, while Leo I and II, which dominate the inertia, are moving apart. They also examined the longevity of the plane via orbital integration.

THEY CONCLUDED that the high anisotropy of the Milky Way’s satellite system can be attributed to its high central concentration, not previously reproduced in simulations, combined with the close but *fleeting* contiguity of its two most distant members.

Compared to previous work, they also found a much higher likelihood of subsets whose orbital poles are as clustered as the Milky Way’s. And although the Milky Way contains such a subset, the ‘plane of satellites’ does not constitute a rotationally supported disk. Instead, it evolves on timescales similar to the ‘transient’ alignments previously found in Λ CDM simulations.

BASED ON the best currently available data, from Gaia, there is, they conclude, no evidence for a ‘plane of satellites’ incompatible with, or even particularly remarkable in, Λ CDM. On the contrary, as judged by the spatial anisotropy of the brightest satellite galaxies, we live in a fairly typical Λ CDM system!